

On direct product pure-1-2-3 subgroups in abelian group $G_n \times G_m$

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Abstract.

In this paper, we shall define new subgroups which are called *pure-1-2-3* in abelian groups $G_n \times G_m$ for all $n, m \in \mathbb{N}$ which are a family of pure subgroups.

In [1], [2] H.M.A. Abdullah gave the some general properties of *pure-1-2-3* in abelian group G , but here, we shall prove more than properties of this subgroups in $\text{Mod } G_n \times G_m$, which are not valid for pure subgroups.

Keywords: Subgroup; Abelian group; Direct product; Pure; Pure-1; Pure-2; Pure-3.

1. Introduction

we shall use following definitions, to get the results.

Definition 1.1 A subgroup S of G said to be *pure-1* in G if for all $x \in S$ and for all prime p , $px = x$.

Remark 1.2

1. If S is *pure-1* in G then $\forall x \in S$ we have $p^{nk} | x$, $n, k \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ in S .
2. Every *pure-1* subgroup is *pure* in G .
3. Every *pure-1* subgroup is divisible.

Definition 1.3.

Let A, B are *pure-1* subgroups in G_n, G_m . Then we shall called a direct product $A \times B$ is *pure-1* in $G_n \times G_m$ if A and B are *pure-1* in G_n, G_m . Which means that $\forall x = (a, b) \in A \times B$ $a \in A, b \in B$ then $p(a, b) = (pa, pb) = (a, b)$.

Now, we are ready to show some results relating to the *direct - pure-1*.

Theorem 1.4 Let $A_1 \times B_1$ and $A_2 \times B_2$ are two direct product *pure-1* in $G_n \times G_m$.

Then

1. $A_1 \times B_1 \cap A_2 \times B_2$ is *pure-1* in $G_n \times G_m$.
2. $A_1 \times B_1 + A_2 \times B_2$ is *pure-1*

Proof.

1. Let $x \in A_1 \times B_1 \cap A_2 \times B_2$ so $x \in A_1 \times B_1$ is *pure-1*, thus $\forall p$

$$p(a, b) = x = (a, b) \in A_1 \times B_1 \quad a \in A_1, b \in B_1.$$

And $A_2 \times B_2$ is *pure-1*, then $p(a_0, b_0) = x = (a_0, b_0) \in A_2 \times B_2$.

Therefore, we get

$$p(a, b) = p(a_0, b_0) = x = (a, b) = (a_0, b_0)$$

Thus, $a = a_0$ and $x = (a, b) \quad b = b_0$

so $px = p(a, b) = (a, b) = x \in A_1 \times B_1 \cap A_2 \times B_2$.

Thus, $A_1 \times B_1 \cap A_2 \times B_2$ is *pure-1*.

2. Let x be any element belong to $A_1 \times B_1 + A_2 \times B_2$

So, $x = ((a_1, b_1), (a_2, b_2)) \quad (a_1, b_1) \in A_1 \times B_1, (a_2, b_2) \in A_2 \times B_2$

but, both $A_1 \times B_1$ and $A_2 \times B_2$ are *pure-1*. Thus $\forall p$

$$p(a_1, b_1) = (a_1, b_1) \tag{1.1}$$

$$p(a_2, b_2) = (a_2, b_2) \tag{1.2}$$

By (1.1) and (1.2) we get

$$p(a_1, b_1) + p(a_2, b_2) = ((a_1, b_1) + (a_2, b_2)) = x$$

$$p((a_1, b_1) + (a_2, b_2)) = x, \text{ but } (a_1, b_1) + (a_2, b_2) \in A_1 \times B_1 + A_2 \times B_2$$

So, $px = x$. We obtain

$A_1 \times B_1 + A_2 \times B_2$ is *pure-1*.

Theorem 1.5 If $A \times B$ is any *pure-1* in $G_n \times G_m$, and $H \times K$ any subgroup of $G_n \times G_m$, then $A \times B \cap H \times K$ is *pure* in $G_n \times G_m$.

Proof.

Let x any element in $A \times B \cap H \times K$. So $x \in A \times B$ and $x \in H \times K$. Since $A \times B$ is a *pure-1* in $G_n \times G_m$, so $\forall p$ (p is prime number)

$$px = x. \quad \text{But } x \in A \times B \cap H \times K.$$

Hence, $A \times B \cap H \times K$ is *pure-1*.

Easily to show the following:

Theorem 1.6

1. If $\bar{A} \times \bar{B}$ is any subgroup of *pure-1* subgroup $\check{A} \times \check{B}$ of $G_n \times G_m$. Then $\bar{A} \times \bar{B}$ is a *pure-1*.
2. If $A \times B$ is a *pure-1* in $G_n \times G_m$ and $\bar{A} \times \bar{B}$ any subgroup of $\check{A} \times \check{B}$ then

$$\frac{A \times B}{A \times B} \text{ is } \textit{pure-1} \text{ in } \frac{G_n \times G_m}{A \times B}$$

Proof.

1. Let $x \in \bar{A} \times \bar{B}$, so $x \in A \times B$ but $A \times B$ is *pure-1* in $G_n \times G_m$, then $\forall p$, we have

$$p(a, b) = (a, b) = x \in \bar{A} \times \bar{B} \text{ for some } a \in A, b \in B.$$

So, $\bar{A} \times \bar{B}$ is *pure-1*.

2. Let $(a, b) + \bar{A} \times \bar{B} \in \frac{A \times B}{A \times B}$.

Since $(a, b) \in A \times B$ and $A \times B$ is a *pure-1* in $G_n \times G_m$. Thus, we have $\forall p, P(a, b) = (a, b)$. Clearly

$$p(a, b) + \bar{A} \times \bar{B} = p((a, b) + \bar{A} \times \bar{B}) = (a, b) + \bar{A} \times \bar{B}. \text{ Thus, } \frac{\check{A} \times \check{B}}{A \times B} \text{ is } \textit{pure-1} \text{ in } \frac{G_n \times G_m}{A \times B}.$$

Definition 1.7 A subgroup $A \times B$ is said to be *pure-2* in $G_n \times G_m$ if $\forall x, x \in A \times B$ and $\forall p, p$ is prime number, then $px = p(px)$.

Remark 1.8

1. It is clear that any *pure-1* is a *pure-2*.
2. $\forall x, x \in A \times B$ and if $A \times B$ is *pure-2* in $G_n \times G_m$, then we are ready to prove the following results of *pure-2*.

Theorem 1.9 Any *pure-2* subgroup of Torsion-free group is *pure-1*.

Proof.

Let $A \times B$ be any *pure-2* in Torsion-free $G_n \times G_m$ and $x \in A \times B$, so $\forall p, px = p(px)$, put $x = (a, b) \in A \times B$, thus $p(a, b) = p(p(a, b))$, which implies that $p(a, b) - p(p(a, b)) = (0, 0)$ so $p((a, b) - (p(a, b))) = (0, 0)$. But $G_n \times G_m$ is a Torsion-free. Then $P(a, b) = (a, b)$, we obtain the result.

Theorem 1.10 Any *pure-2* subgroup of Torsion-free group is

1. *pure*.
2. *pure-1*.

Proof.

1. Let $A \times B$ be any *pure-2* in $G_n \times G_m$, we claim that $A \times B$ is a neat in $G_n \times G_m$.

Let $x \in A \times B$, and suppose that $\forall p, p \mid_x$ in $G_n \times G_m$, so $x \in p_{G_n \times G_m} \bigcap A \times B$. Thus,

$$x = p(g_n, g_m) \text{ for some } g_n \in G_n, g_m \in G_m. \tag{1.3}$$

Since $A \times B$ is a *pure-2*, so we can write $px = p(px)$,

so $p(p(g_n, g_m)) = pp(x) \Rightarrow p^2(g_n, g_m) = p^2x$ but $G_n \times G_m$ is Torsion-free we get $(g_n, g_m) = x$ by (1.3) we can obtain $x = (g_n, g_m) = p(g_n, g_m) \in p(A \times B)$.

Which means that $p \mid_x \in A \times B$, by ([3] p.q2) We get the result.

2. Let $A \times B$ be any *pure-2* in a Torsion-free $G_n \times G_m$ for all $x \in A \times B$, so for all prime p we have $px = p(px)$, and let $x = (a, b)$ for some $a \in A, b \in B$ then, $p(a, b) = p(p(a, b))$, But $G_n \times G_m$ is a Torsion-free group. Thus, $p((a, b) - p(a, b)) = 0$ which implies that $(a, b) = p(a, b)$ and we we get . But $\forall (a, b) \in A \times B$ and for all prime p , $p \mid_{(a,b)}$ in $A \times B$. Moreover, $A \times B$ is a Neat in $G_n \times G_m$.

By the above theorems we get the main results:

Theorem 1.11 Let $G_n \times G_m$ be a Torsion-free group then the following statements are equivalent:

1. $A \times B$ is a *pure-1*;
2. $A \times B$ is a *pure-2*;
3. $A \times B$ is a *pure*.

Theorem 1.12 If $A \times B$ is *pure-2* and a Neat subgroup of $G_n \times G_m$ then $A \times B$ is *pure*.

Proof.

Since $A \times B$ is a Neat in $G_n \times G_m$, then we have $p(G_n \times G_m) \bigcap A \times B = p(A \times B)$, $\forall p, p$ is prime number. we shall prove the statement by induction.

So let $\forall p$ and $\forall k \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

$$P^k G_n \times G_m \bigcap A \times B = P^k(A \times B) \text{ is true.}$$

We have to show that

$$P^k G_n \times G_m \bigcap A \times B = P^{k+1}(A \times B).$$

The induction $P^{k+1}(A \times B) \subseteq P^{k+1} G_n \times G_m \bigcap A \times B$ is obvious.

Remained to show that $P^{k+1} G_n \times G_m \bigcap A \times B \subseteq P^{k+1}(A \times B)$.

Let $(a, b) \in P^{k+1} G_n \times G_m \bigcap A \times B$ and we may write (a, b) in the form $(a, b) = P^{k+1}(g_n, g_m)$ for some $(g_n, g_m) \in G_n \times G_m$. Thus, $(a, b) = P^k(p(g_n, g_m)) \in A \times B \bigcap P^k G_n \times G_m$ but $A \times B$ is a Neat. Thus,

$$(a, b) = P^k(P(g_n, g_m)) \in A \times B \bigcap P^k G_n \times G_m = P^k(A \times B).$$

Therefore,

$(a, b) = P^k(a_0, b_0)$ for some $(a_0, b_0) \in A \times B$. Since $A \times B$ is *pure-2*, then we get

$(a, b) = P^k(a_0, b_0) = P^{k-1}(P(a_0, b_0)) = P^{k-1}(P(P(a_0, b_0))) = P^{k+1}(a_0, b_0) \in P^{k+1}A \times B$. Assuming $k \geq 1$.
So $A \times B \cap P^{k+1}(G_n \times G_m) = P^{k+1}(A \times B)$. Consequently $A \times B$ is a *pure*

Now we shall prove some properties of *pure-2* subgroups, which are valid in *pure-1* .

Theorem 1.13 *If $A \times B$ is a pure-2 subgroup of $G_n \times G_m$ then:*

1. $A \times B \cap C \times D$ is also *pure-2* for any subgroup $C \times D$ of $G_n \times G_m$.
2. If $A \times B$ is a *pure-2* subgroup of $G_n \times G_m$ then any subgroup of $A \times B$ is also *pure-2* .
3. The sum of any two *pure-2* subgroups of $G_n \times G_m$ will be *pure-2* .
4. If $A \times B$ is a *pure-2* subgroup of $A \times B$, then $A \times B/c \times D$ is *pure-2* .

Definition 1.14 *A subgroup $A \times B$ of $G_n \times G_m$ is called pure-3 if $(\forall p)$, $(\forall k \in Z^+$ and $\forall(a, b) \in A \times B$*

$$P^k(a, b) = P^k(P(a, b)) = P^{k+1}(a, b)$$

Remark 1.15

1. Any *pure-2* is *pure-3* .
2. If $k = 1$, then a *pure-3* is a *pure-2* .

Now, we are ready to prove the following results of *pure-3* subgroups.

Theorem 1.16 *If $A \times B$ is pure-3 and Neat subgroup of $G_n \times G_m$, then $A \times B$ is a pure.*

Proof.

Since $A \times B$ is *pure-3* , then we have $\forall p, P(G_n \times G_m) \cap A \times B = P(A \times B)$.

We will prove the statement by induction. Let $(\forall p), (\forall k), P^k(G_n \times G_m) \cap A \times B = P(A \times B)$ is true, so we have to showing that

$$P^{k-1}(G_n \times G_m) \cap A \times B = P^{k+1}(A \times B) .$$

Let $(a, b) = P^{k+1}(g_n, g_m)$ for some $(g_n, g_m) \in G_n \times G_m$. Thus,

$$(a, b) = P^{k+1}(g_n, g_m) \in A \times B \cap P^k(G_n \times G_m) = P_k(A \times B) .$$

Therefore, $(a, b) = P^k(a_0, b_0)$ for some $(a_0, b_0) \in A \times B$. Since $A \times B$ is *pure-3* , then $(a, b) = P^k(a_0, b_0) = P^k(P(a_0, b_0)) \in P^{k+1}(A \times B)$.

Consequently $A \times B$ is *pure* .

Now, we shall give the generalization of the Theorem 1.10.

Theorem 1.17 Any pure-3 subgroup of Torsion-free $G_n \times G_m$ is pure

Theorem 1.18 Any pure-3 subgroup of a torsion-free abelian group G is pure-1

Proof.

Let $A \times B$ be a pure in a free $G_n \times G_m$, let $(a, b) \in A \times B$, then $(\forall p), k \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ we have $P^k(a, b) = P^k(p(a, b))$ (Assume that $k \geq 1$). So $P^k((a, b) - P(a, b)) = 0$ and since G is torsion-free, then $P(a, b) - (a, b) = 0$ So $(a, b) = P(a, b)$, we obtain that $A \times B$ is pure-1.

We know that the intersection of divisible (pure), (Neat) subgroup is not divisible (pure-Neat). But we shall show that if $A \times B$ and $A_1 \times B_1$ are two pure-3 and Neat in $G_n \times G_m$ then $A \times B \cap A_1 \times B_1$ is pure.

First we need the following lemma:

Lemma 1.19 Let $A \times B$ be a pure-3 in $G_n \times G_m$ and $A_1 \times B_1$, be any subgroup of $G_n \times G_m$. Then $P^k(A \times B \cap A_1 \times B_1) = P^k A \times B \cap P^k A_1 \times B_1, (\forall p) (\forall k, k \in \mathbb{Z}^+.$

Proof.

Let $(a, b) \in P^k A \times B \cap P^k A_1 \times B_1$. Therefore, $(a, b) = P^k(a_0, b_0)$ for some $(a_0, b_0) \in A \times B$. Since $A \times B$ is pure-3. Then $P^k(a, b) = P^{2k}(a, b) = P^k(a_0, b_0)$. Then $(a_0, b_0) = P^k(a, b) \in P^k(A \times B \cap A_1 \times B_1)$ we obtain the result.

Remark 1.20 The above lemma is satisfied for pure-1-2 subgroups.

Theorem 1.21 Let $A \times B$ and $A_1 \times B_1$ be two pure-3 and Neat in $G_n \times G_m$. Then $A \times B \cap A_1 \times B_1$.

Proof.

By using Theorem 1.16 we have $A \times B$ and $A_1 \times B_1$ are pure. We need to prove $A \times B \cap A_1 \times B_1$ is pure.

Let $(a, b) \in A \times B \cap A_1 \times B_1$ and let us suppose that $P|^k(a, b)$ is solvable in $G_n \times G_m$. Then $(a, b) = P^k(g_n, g_m)$ for some $(g_n, g_m) \in G_n \times G_m$. Since $A \times B$ and $A_1 \times B_1$ are pure. Then $P^k(a_0, b_0) = (a, b) = P^k(a_1, b_1)$ for some $(a_0, b_0) \in A \times B, (a_1, b_1) \in A_1 \times B_1$ By lemma 1.19 we have

$P^k(A \times B) \cap P^k A_1 \times B_1 = P^k(A \times B \cap A_1 \times B_1)$. Then $(a, b) = P^k(y, z)$ for some $(y, z) \in A \times B \cap A_1 \times B_1$.

Consequently, $A \times B \cap A_1 \times B_1$ is pure.

Now, we are showing the following results:

Theorem 1.22 Let $P(S \times M)$ be a *pure-2* in $G_n \times G_m$. Then $P(S \times M)$ is *pure*.

Proof.

Claim $P(S \times M)$ is Neat. We have to show that $P(G_n \times G_m) \cap P(S \times M) = P(P(S \times M))$.

Let $(a, b) = P(g_n, g_m) = P(S, M) \in P(S \times M)$ since $P(S \times M)$ is *pure-2*,

$P(S, M) = P(P(S, M))$, so $(a, b) = P(S, M) = P(P(S, M)) \in P(P(S \times M))$. Consequently $P(S \times M)$ is Neat. By theorems (1.12, 1.13) We obtain that $P(S \times M)$ is *pure* in $G_n \times G_m$.

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